

Limits of slenderness ratios for URM walls: proposal for EC8-Part 1

Background document for the masonry chapter in EC8 Part 1

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Changes: Calculations were repeated for $q=1.25$ (previously: 1.0); old tables are still included and new tables are added

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1 Objectives of this document

This document puts forward a proposal for slenderness limits to be used for unreinforced masonry (URM) walls. If these slenderness limits are met, out-of-plane safety checks do not need to be explicitly conducted.

All Mathematica-files that were used to compute the slenderness limits are made publicly available through the Zenodo repository.

2 Derivation of slenderness limits for URM walls

2.1 Assumptions and case studies considered for the derivation

For the derivation of the slenderness limits we consider URM walls that are subjected to out-of-plane loading. Moreover, we model storey-high one-way bending walls and neglect two-way bending mechanisms. The assumption of one-way bending walls is on the safe side as two-way bending mechanisms generally exhibit higher force and displacement capacities than one-way mechanisms ([1], [2]). Based on this assumption, out-of-plane loaded walls are modelled as 2D systems of one-way bending vertical wall strips. It is assumed that the walls are not stiffened by stiffening elements on their vertical edges.

Slenderness ratios are derived for the wall configurations illustrated in Figure 1, which are:

- (a) Walls spanning between two floors. These walls are located at the upper floors of a building, where axial forces are the lowest and accelerations the highest;
- (b) Parapet walls or chimneys located at the top of a building, with no axial load applied. These latter can also be taken as proxy of gable walls that are not supported at the top.

Figure 1 Configurations of URM walls for which limits of slenderness ratio are derived: (a) walls spanning between two floors and (b) parapet walls and chimneys. Geometry and failure mechanism.

2.2 Definition of slenderness ratio

The slenderness ratio is defined according to the EC6 7.5.1.1(5) [3] as the ratio between the effective height h_{eff} and the effective thickness t_{eff} of the wall.

For the two wall configurations herein considered, the effective height h_{eff} is defined as in the EC6 7.5.1.2. In particular:

- (a) For walls spanning between two floors (Figure 1a), it is assumed that no restraints or stiffening elements are present on the wall vertical edges (see point 7.5.1.2(9)) and that the walls are restrained at the top and the bottom by reinforced-concrete floors providing adequate restraint to rotation (7.5.1.2(10)(ii)); for such wall configuration: $h_{\text{eff}} = 0.75 h_w$, with h_w the wall clear height;

- (b) For parapet walls and chimneys (Figure 1b), this wall configuration falls within the class of '*walls that have no top and no side restraint, but to which load may be applied, provided that the base of the wall is fully restrained*' defined at point 7.5.1.2(10)(i), for which $h_{\text{eff}} = 2 h_w$, with h_w the parapet clear height. Parapet walls might also be taken as proxy for gable walls that are not supported at the top and the side edges.

The effective thickness t_{eff} is defined according to the EC6 7.5.1.3(1) as equal to the actual thickness of the wall t_w , since stiffening elements perpendicular to the URM wall, for which point 7.5.1.3(2) would apply, are not taken into consideration in the analysis.

2.3 Methodology used for the derivation

Limits on the slenderness $h_{\text{eff}}/t_{\text{eff}}$ ratio for the two wall configurations (a) and (b) of Figure 1 are derived by making use of the force-based seismic assessment method contained in the commentary [4] to the Italian technical standard [5] (for a review on this and other assessment methods, see [6]). The method, which is recommended for safety checks, is herein used for design purposes. Note that not the latest version of the Italian technical standard was considered. The calculations should be repeated considering any changes in the latest version of the Italian technical standard.

Force-based method

The method is based on the linear kinematic analysis of the wall [7], which allows computing the load multiplier that triggers the mechanism, α_0 , based on the rigid body analysis of the wall. The corresponding spectral acceleration a_0^* is calculated starting from α_0 through the guidelines in [4] (see also [6]). For walls located at higher levels of the structure, the force-based method consists in checking whether [4]:

$$a_0^* \geq \frac{S_{a,j}}{q} \quad (1)$$

where $S_{a,j}$ is the storey response spectrum and q is the q-factor. According to the Italian technical standard [4],[5], the above check is applicable to the Damage Limit State for $q = 1$ and to the Life-Safety Limit State for $q = 2$. Slenderness limitations are derived for the Life-Safety Limit State. As illustrated in [8], in order to be conservative a q-factor of 1 is nonetheless considered also for the Life-Safety Limit State.

Storey response spectrum definition

The storey response spectrum is computed as follows:

- a) For walls spanning between two floors (Figure 1a), $S_{a,j}$ is evaluated through Eq. (7.22) contained in the new EC8 draft:

$$S_{a,j} = \frac{PFA_j}{\left| \left(\frac{T_a}{T_1} \right)^2 - 1 \right|} \sqrt{1 + \left[\left(\frac{T_a}{T_1} \right)^2 \frac{S_{e,a}}{S_{ep,1}} q_D \right]^2}, \quad (2)$$

respecting the conditions: $S_{a,j} > S_e(T_A)$ and $S_{a,j} < AMP \times PFA_j$.

AMP is the amplification factor defined by Eq. (7.23):

$$AMP = 2.5 \sqrt{\frac{10}{5+\xi_a}}, \text{ for } \frac{T_1}{T_C} = 0(3)$$

$$\text{linear versus } \frac{T_1}{T_C}, \text{ for } \frac{T_1}{T_C} \leq 0.2$$

$$\frac{10}{\sqrt{\xi_a}}, \text{ for } \frac{T_1}{T_C} \geq 0.2$$

where: ξ_a is the critical damping ratio of the non-structural element, here set to 5%, which is the lowest damping ratio observed for rocking walls [7]; T_1 is the fundamental period of the structure; T_a is the natural fundamental period of the wall; $S_{ep,1} = S_e(T_1)$ is elastic spectrum evaluated at T_1 ; $S_{e,a} = S_e(T_A)$, with T_A the first corner period of the elastic spectrum; T_C is the third corner period of the elastic spectrum given in 5.2.2.2.

PFA_j is the peak floor acceleration defined by Eq. (7.20):

$$PFA_j = \Gamma_1 \left(\frac{z_j}{H} \right)^k \left(\frac{S_{ep,1}}{q_D} \right) \quad (4)$$

where: PFA_j is the peak floor acceleration; z_j is the height of the center of the wall measured from the building foundation; H is the building height; q_D is the primary structure behavior factor component accounting for deformation capacity and energy dissipation capacity, as defined at point 6.3.2 of the new EC8 draft; $\Gamma_1 = \frac{2k+1}{k+1} \frac{2N}{2N+1}$ is the participation factor of the 1st mode of vibration, with N the number of levels; k is a factor taking into account whether the structure undergoes a shear or a bending deformation.

- b) For parapet walls and chimneys (Figure 1b), according to the new draft of EC8 these elements can be regarded as rigid ($T_a/T_1 < 0.2$) and the storey response spectrum can therefore be determined by Eq. (7.19):

$$S_{a,j} = PFA_j \quad (5)$$

where PFA_j is the peak floor acceleration defined in Eq. (4).

Note that the height of the center of the wall z_j should consider the boundary conditions at the top and bottom of the wall:

- (a) For walls spanning between two floors with the same boundary conditions at the top and bottom, z_j corresponds to the position of the geometric center of the wall;
- (b) For parapet walls or chimneys that are free at the top but cast in at the bottom, z_j corresponds to the position of the base of the wall.

Moreover, the behavior factor q_D is set equal to 1.5 and $k = 1$. The fundamental period of the building is calculated as $T_1 = 0.075 H^{0.75}$ [9]. The elastic response spectrum S_e is expressed according to Eqs. (5.4)-(5.10) of the draft, in terms of the reference spectral acceleration $S_{\alpha RP}$, plus factors depending on the site category and the seismicity level. The resulting spectra are illustrated in Figure 2.

Outline of the methodology used for derivation

By using the above definitions, relationships between the wall slenderness and the PGA that the wall can sustain are derived as follows:

1. The spectral acceleration a_0^* is first calculated; for both wall configurations, this quantity is expressed as function of the wall slenderness h_{eff}/t_{eff} ;
2. Eq. (1) is then used to equate a_0^* to the floor spectrum $S_{a,j}$ which for walls spanning between two floors and parapet walls is evaluated by using respectively Eq. (2) and (5). In particular, for walls spanning between two floors, $S_{a,j}$ is evaluated for $T_a = T_1$, which leads to the largest amplification of the response spectrum. For parapet walls, $S_{a,j}$ is evaluated by using as fundamental period the corner period T_B ; as a consequence, a_0^* equates the plateau of the storey response spectra $S_{a,j}$ and its value is the same for all seismicity levels.
3. The slenderness limits are derived by plugging said $S_{a,j}$ into Eq. (1). The limits are initially function of $S_{\alpha RP}$ for each site category and are finally expressed as function of the PGA after setting $PGA = S_{\alpha RP}/2.5$. For the derivation, assumptions on the axial load applied at the wall top are taken.

Figure 2 Response spectrum for different site categories and seismic levels, as defined in the current draft of EC8.

Starting from the relationships between slenderness and PGA, slenderness limits are found for each site category and seismicity level, by taking the $h_{\text{eff}}/t_{\text{eff}}$ value that corresponds to the upper bound of the range of acceleration given for each seismicity level and 6 m/s^2 for high seismicity. The new draft of EC8 defines the seismicity levels in terms of reference spectral acceleration on site category A and for a reference return period of 475 years (Table 5.2 contained therein):

$$\begin{aligned} \text{low seismicity (m/s}^2\text{):} & \quad 1 \leq S_{\alpha 475} \leq 2.5 \\ \text{moderate seismicity (m/s}^2\text{):} & \quad 2.5 \leq S_{\alpha 475} \leq 5 \\ \text{high seismicity (m/s}^2\text{):} & \quad S_{\alpha 475} \geq 5 \end{aligned}$$

The upper bounds for low and moderate seismicity approximately correspond to a PGA of $0.1g$ and $0.2g$; for high seismicity levels, an acceleration of $0.25g$ is used as an upper bound. This acceleration corresponds to the highest seismicity level given in the Italian seismic map, excluding points of the map where specific seismic conditions apply.

The derivation of slenderness limits for the two wall configurations is detailed in the following sections.

2.4 Prototype of building and walls considered in this study

As prototype for the building we consider a 2-storey structure ($N = 2$). Moreover, the wall is located at the highest level of the structure: $z_j/H = 0.75$. For the case of a wall spanning between two floors, we assume that the wall is clamped at the top and at the bottom. For a wall located at the uppermost storey of the building two overburden ratios are considered: $\omega = 1.5$ and $\omega = 2.25$. These two ratios allow distinguishing between walls respectively made of solid stone masonry units and hollow bricks (artificial units).

2.5 Derivation for walls spanning between two floors

It is assumed that in modern URM buildings, URM walls span between two floors (Figure 1a). For this reason, in the following, a wall strip of height h_w , length l_w , thickness t_w , and self-weight W is considered. The wall, subjected to a vertical load O and to lateral inertia forces, undergoes a failure mechanism characterized by two macroblocks separated by a fully cracked section [7], [10].

The position of that section, which represents the middle hinge, can be determined by minimization of the load multiplier, according to the kinematic theorem of limit analysis. For simplicity, it is here assumed that the middle section is located at the wall mid-height. For the level of overburden considered in the derivation, this assumption brings to a relative error of < 1% in estimating α_0^* .

With this methodology, the maximum load multiplier is

$$\alpha_0 = \frac{3t_{\text{eff}}(1+2\omega)}{h_{\text{eff}}} \quad (6)$$

and the maximum spectral acceleration is:

$$\alpha_0^* = \alpha_0 g \quad (7)$$

where $h_{\text{eff}} = 0.75h_w$ and $\omega = O/W$ is the overburden ratio which is the ratio between the axial force O and the body weight of the wall W .

Based on these ratios, Eq. (1) is solved in terms of $h_{\text{eff}}/t_{\text{eff}}$ and keeping the PGA as a free variable. Curves of the type $h_{\text{eff}}/t_{\text{eff}} = f(\xi/PGA)$, with ξ a scalar, are thus obtained. These curves are given in Figure 3 for an overburden ratio O/W of 1.5.

Figure 3 Slenderness ratio vs PGA – walls spanning between two floors with overburden ratio O/W of 1.5.

Table 1 and Table 2 contain the resulting slenderness limits for walls spanning between two floors resulting from the applied methodology for, respectively, $O/W = 1.5$ and $O/W = 2.25$. The obtained values are limited by the maximum slenderness limit of 27 given in EC6 7.5.2(1) [3].

Previous version (July 2019): $q = 1.0$

Low Seismicity evaluated at 2.5 m/s^2 , Moderate @ 5 m/s^2 , High @ 6 m/s^2

Table 1 $h_{\text{eff}}/t_{\text{eff}}$ limits for walls spanning between two floors with $O/W = 1.5$ based on the seismicity level

	Low Seismicity	Moderate Seismicity	High Seismicity with $S_{a475} \leq 6.0 \text{ m/s}^2$
Site Category A	25	9	7
Site Category B	16	7	6
Site Category C	13	6	5
Site Category D	12	6	5
Site Category E	10	5	4

Site Category F	13	6	5
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Table 2 h_{eff}/t_{eff} limits for walls spanning between two floors with O/W = 2.25 based on the seismicity level

	Low Seismicity	Moderate Seismicity	High Seismicity with $S_{\alpha 475} \leq 6.0 \text{ m/s}^2$
Site Category A	27	12	10
Site Category B	22	10	8
Site Category C	18	9	7
Site Category D	16	8	7
Site Category E	14	7	6
Site Category F	18	9	7

New version - Pt 1 (April 2020): $q = 1.25$

Low Seismicity evaluated at 2.5 m/s^2 , Moderate @ 5 m/s^2 , High @ 6 m/s^2

Table 3 h_{eff}/t_{eff} limits for walls spanning between two floors with O/W = 1.5 based on the seismicity level

	Low Seismicity	Moderate Seismicity	High Seismicity with $S_{\alpha 475} \leq 6.0 \text{ m/s}^2$
Site Category A	27.	11.	9.
Site Category B	20.	9.	8.
Site Category C	16.	8.	7.
Site Category D	15.	7.	6.
Site Category E	13.	6.	5.
Site Category F	16.	8.	7.

Table 4 h_{eff}/t_{eff} limits for walls spanning between two floors with O/W = 2.25 based on the seismicity level

	Low Seismicity	Moderate Seismicity	High Seismicity with $S_{\alpha 475} \leq 6.0 \text{ m/s}^2$
Site Category A	27.	15.	13.
Site Category B	27.	13.	10.
Site Category C	22.	11.	9.
Site Category D	20.	10.	8.
Site Category E	18.	9.	7.
Site Category F	22.	11.	9.

2.6 Derivation for parapet walls and chimneys

The same methodology is applied to the case of a parapet wall or chimney with no axial load at the top. The wall undergoes an overturning, or cantilever-type of failure mechanism (Figure 1b).

For this configuration, we derive:

$$\alpha_0 = 2 \frac{t_{eff}}{h_{eff}} \quad (8)$$

and:

$$\alpha_0^* = \frac{4}{3} \alpha_0 g \quad (9)$$

where $h_{\text{eff}} = 2h_w$. Evaluating α_0^* , the participating mass has been taken as $\frac{3}{4}$ the wall mass. As prototype for the building we consider a two-storey structure ($N = 2$); Moreover, the wall is located at the top of the structure: $z_j/H = 1$. The obtained $h_{\text{eff}}/t_{\text{eff}}$ vs PGA curves are given in Figure 4.

Table 53 contains the resulting slenderness limits for parapet walls and chimneys.

Figure 4 Slenderness ratio vs PGA – parapet walls or chimneys with no axial load.

Previous version (July 2019): $q = 1.0$

Low Seismicity evaluated at 2.5 m/s^2 , Moderate @ 5 m/s^2 , High @ 6 m/s^2

Table 5 $h_{\text{eff}}/t_{\text{eff}}$ limits for parapet walls or chimneys based on the seismicity level

	Low Seismicity	Moderate Seismicity	High Seismicity with $S_{\alpha 475} \leq 6.0 \text{ m/s}^2$
Site Category A	13	7	5
Site Category B	11	5	5
Site Category C	10	5	4
Site Category D	9	4	4
Site Category E	8	4	3
Site Category F	10	5	4

New version - Pt 1 (April 2020): $q = 1.25$

Low Seismicity evaluated at 2.5 m/s^2 , Moderate @ 5 m/s^2 , High @ 6 m/s^2

Table 6 $h_{\text{eff}}/t_{\text{eff}}$ limits for parapet walls or chimneys based on the seismicity level

	Low Seismicity	Moderate Seismicity	High Seismicity with $S_{\alpha 475} \leq 6.0 \text{ m/s}^2$
Site Category A	16.	8.	7.
Site Category B	14.	7.	6.
Site Category C	12.	6.	5.
Site Category D	11.	5.	5.
Site Category E	10.	5.	4.
Site Category F	12.	6.	5.

3 Recommendations for slenderness limits

Table 94 and Table 105 contain the proposals for slenderness limits for walls spanning between two floors and for parapet walls and chimneys, respectively. The latter class of walls can be intended as URM walls without overburden.

The values contained in the tables are derived from the values in Table 1 and Table 2 for spanning walls and from Table 53 for parapet walls. They are derived from Site Categories B and C. Values for stone units in Table 94 come from Table 1. Values from hollow bricks are from Table 2. Values for parapet walls make no distinction between stone and hollow bricks as they are all derived from the case of walls without overburden, which is given in Table 53.

For walls belonging to regions of seismicity higher than as indicated in the table (0.25g), it is suggested that engineers make more specific safety check calculations.

Note that it is recommended to keep $t_{eff,min}$ as NDP because $t_{eff,min}$ is at present not determined by mechanical calculations. It is thinkable that such limits are determined on the basis of size effects of rocking bodies. However, the here applied approach cannot seize size effects and therefore the minimum thickness cannot be derived.

Table 7 Proposal for h_{eff}/t_{eff} limits for walls spanning between two floors (based on $q=1.0$, July 2019)

Unreinforced masonry typology	$h_{eff}/t_{eff} _{max}$
Regular stone units	7
Regular stone units, low seismicity	15
All other units	10
All other units, low seismicity	20

Table 8 Proposal for h_{eff}/t_{eff} limits for parapet walls or chimneys (based on $q=1.0$, July 2019)

Unreinforced masonry typology	$h_{eff}/t_{eff} _{max}$
Regular stone units	5
Regular stone units, low seismicity	10
All other units	5
All other units, low seismicity	10

Table 9 Proposal for h_{eff}/t_{eff} limits for walls spanning between two floors (based on $q=1.25$, July 2019)

Unreinforced masonry typology	$h_{eff}/t_{eff} _{max}$
Regular stone units	8
Regular stone units, low seismicity	16
All other units	11
All other units, low seismicity	22

Table 10 Proposal for h_{eff}/t_{eff} limits for parapet walls or chimneys (based on $q=1.25$, July 2019)

Unreinforced masonry typology	$h_{eff}/t_{eff} _{max}$
Regular stone units	6
Regular stone units, low seismicity	12
All other units	6
All other units, low seismicity	12

4 Comparison with slenderness limits in current EC8-Part

1

The current EC8-Part 1 [11] specifies maximum slenderness ratios of $\frac{h_{eff}}{t_{eff}} = 12$ for masonry built with artificial units and relaxes this limit to $\frac{h_{eff}}{t_{eff}} = 15$ in case of low seismicity (Table 116). For natural stone units a stricter limit of $\frac{h_{eff}}{t_{eff}} = 9$ applies.

Table 11 Geometric requirements for masonry shear walls in current EC8-Part 1 [11]

Masonry type	$t_{eff,min}$ (mm)	$\left(\frac{h_{eff}}{t_{eff}}\right)_{max}$	$\left(\frac{l}{h}\right)_{min}$
Unreinforced, with natural stone units	350	9	0,5
Unreinforced, with any other type of units	240	12	0,4
Unreinforced, with any other type of units, in cases of low seismicity	170	15	0,35
Confined masonry	240	15	0,3
Reinforced masonry	240	15	No restriction

Symbols used have the following meaning:

t_{ef} thickness of the wall (see EN 1996-1-1:2004);
 h_{ef} effective height of the wall (see EN 1996-1-1:2004);
 h greater clear height of the openings adjacent to the wall;
 l length of the wall.

5 References

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